

THE RELEVANCE OF INTEGRATIONAL LESSONS IN THE IMPROVEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL LESSONS

Berdikulova Nasiba Erkinjonovna

Samarkand State University named after Sharaf Rashidov

Annotation: In the context of the modernization of education, the tasks of a modern school are changing. The most important priorities for students are individual development, awareness of their position in society, independence, readiness for self-determination, that is, those qualities without which it is impossible to modernize the country and join the community of developed countries. To solve this problem, it is necessary to create a learning system that would correspond to the formation of systemic knowledge among schoolchildren without harming their health. Psychological and pedagogical thought and education are in constant search of methods, forms, and techniques that contribute to the creation of such a system.

Keywords: technological progress, teaching methods, historical significance

One of the directions in this search is the implementation of interdisciplinary connections in education. The relevance of interdisciplinary relations at this stage of society's development is obvious, this is a requirement of the time. It is conditioned by the current level of scientific and technological progress, the strengthening of integrative trends in science, technology, and production. And this problem of school education remains unresolved. The multidimensional nature of the curriculum, the weak coherence of scientific discourses (arguments) presented in the content of academic subjects, the gap between knowledge and the personality of the student and other reasons lead to fragmented learning.

Presentation of the main material of the article. In modern conditions, the formation of a personality with diverse knowledge is recognized as a priority goal

of educational systems. Achieving the integrity of general education, the coherence of its substantive, organizational, procedural and personal development components become the primary task of the teacher. Success in forming a unified system of scientific knowledge about living and inanimate nature becomes possible if education is conducted in the interrelation and interaction of related subjects, in particular subjects of literature and history.

The principle of the integrity of the image of the world requires the selection of such educational content that will help the student to maintain and recreate the integrity of the picture of the world, ensure their awareness of the various connections between objects and phenomena, and at the same time - the formation of the ability to see the same subject from different sides. Cognitive activity of students is possible only where certain conditions are created for its development. And the integration of the educational process plays a huge role in this. When implementing an integrative approach to learning, it is very important to take into account the child's health, because such lessons require greater concentration, concentration, the use of analysis and synthesis techniques, etc. During my time at school, I have tested traditional teaching methods. But preference is given to the use of integrated learning technology, as it gives the most effective result. Interdisciplinary integration does not negate the subject system. It is an important way to improve it, overcome shortcomings and is aimed at deepening the relationship and interdependence between subjects. Meaningful and purposeful integrated lessons bring novelty and originality to the usual structure of school education, and have a certain advantage for students:

- they are built taking into account the individual characteristics of the child, taking into account his age and psychological characteristics;
- increase motivation, form interest, which contributes to self-education, increase the level of learning and education of students;

- contribute to the formation of a holistic picture of the world, consideration of the subject from several sides: theoretical, practical, applied;
- allow you to systematize knowledge;
- contribute to the development, to a greater extent than ordinary lessons, of aesthetic perception, imagination, attention, memory, and creative thinking of students.

The problem of integrating education and upbringing in secondary school is important and modern. Its relevance is dictated by the new social demands placed on the school. The modern education system is aimed at the formation of a highly educated, intellectually developed personality with a holistic view of the world, with an understanding of the depth of connections between phenomena and processes of the surrounding world. Subject disunity becomes one of the reasons for the fragmented worldview of a school graduate, while in the modern world trends towards economic, political, cultural, and information integration prevail.

It turned out that quite imperceptibly in one lesson stories about Orthodox shrines and holy ascetics of land and secular songs about the small and large Homeland were intertwined. But if all of them touched the souls of children, then we are on the right path of spiritual, patriotic enlightenment and moral education of our children. As a creative task, students were asked to draw the Don sights with a brief description of their historical significance, with further protection of the project in front of an audience of classmates.

According to the results of the lessons, in conversations with students and through the study of mini-essays, we found that children harmoniously systematized their ideas about the studied historical epochs, historical figures, and formed concepts of cause-and-effect relationships between actions, events, and facts. Thanks to the knowledge gained, the images created in the lessons, the experience of the feelings of historical characters passed through children's perception, there was an awareness of the sequence of certain historical events.

The conclusion is that students build their education only on interest, not seeing the methodological significance of the fact that the studied sciences have common concepts, laws, and use the same research methods. Therefore, in our lessons, we strive to ensure that when moving from intra-subject connections to intrasubject ones, the student learns to transfer methods of action from one subject to another, which facilitates learning, forms an idea of the integrity of the world and serves as a matrix for the increment of new knowledge. At the same time, interest develops into sustainable educational, cognitive and creative activities. When planning and organizing integrated lessons, the teacher should take into account that such lessons combine blocks of knowledge of two or three different subjects, therefore it is extremely correct to determine the main purpose of the lesson.

Within the framework of an integrated lesson, teachers can determine in advance what is considered important and what is secondary in order to teach their students to rationally design their work, correctly build oral answers, instill in them self-control and self-esteem skills, etc. Lessons based on similar teacher interaction are also classified as integrated, although the material being studied on them, it may not overlap with each other in any way."The most common are the lessons of the second and third level of integration. By the second level, we mean the unification of the conceptual and information sphere of educational subjects. Such lessons can be conducted in order to best memorize any facts and information, concomitant repetition, and introduction of additional material to the topic. The third level is related to the tasks of comparative and generalizing study of the material and is expressed in the ability of schoolchildren to compare and contrast phenomena and objects. And here, as in previous cases, it is necessary to observe the basic conditions: if a lesson is taught by one teacher, then there should be a paired lesson by a second subject teacher, where the same facts and problems are analyzed. Therefore, mutual visits of teachers are very useful in order to coordinate and adjust pedagogical actions.

So far, we have talked about the principles of integration. And what forms of integrated lessons can there be? It should be noted once again that they can be led by one teacher. The role of the second one will then consist in the joint development of a lesson system, setting goals, tasks, preparing classes, selecting material, as well as in the presence of a colleague in the classroom, so that their lessons can be built in accordance with general plans, with mandatory references to the material of another subject, thereby activating in the minds of schoolchildren ideas about the relationship of educational disciplines. Of course, you need to attend not only explanation lessons, but also consolidation and generalization of knowledge, credits, protection of creative works, if any.

There is also a conditionally negative fact of integration in the methodology of primary language teaching - this is a set of programs of the twenties. The reasons for the failure of these programs are easily explained if they are considered in terms of the levels and possibilities of integrating academic subjects in primary education. And the idea of integration in them was clearly visible. There is a unity of purpose: by integrating objects into complexes, the authors dreamed of creating a liberated, creative personality. Complexes, according to the authors of the programs, were those parts or elements, the totality of which was supposed to make learning interesting, connected with life, stimulating and nourishing the creative initiative of children. Thus, it would seem, everything was taken into account. The only thing that was not taken into account was that a broad interdisciplinary model of integration in primary schools is productive only if it is based on elementary but solid skills available to children, i.e. the integration of subjects already assumes that students have such a base. Thus, the younger the student, the less he knows and knows, the more limited the possibilities for integrating academic subjects are for him. However, the fact of integrating the literacy course and the basics of reader's independence takes a different turn. This type of activity was immediately the leading means of learning. In view of this, integration is undeniable here. In this

case, it is simply impossible to do without it, if we seriously talk about teaching as the formation of a personality, its self-development and self-education. Of course, other subjects are integrated into primary education, but still, the norm for primary classes is the elements of integration in academic subjects, and not integrated courses.

Integrated lessons relieve students' fatigue and overexertion by switching from one type of activity to another. However, as noted above, in the first two years of schooling, integration should not be particularly emphasized, because the child does not yet have a large amount of knowledge, grammatical, computational, and technical skills have not been formed. In addition, one of the mandatory and basic requirements of integrated teaching is to increase the role of student independence, because integration inevitably expands the subject of the material being studied, necessitates a deeper analysis and generalization of phenomena, the range of which increases at the expense of other subjects. Is it feasible for students to study such a volume of material on their own? Students will cope with such work only if they know the techniques of research and are able to organize their time correctly. These questions should be faced by a primary school teacher who is seriously engaged in the problem of integration at this stage of learning.

Literatures:

1. Lysakova Zh.A. Formation of theoretical concepts in the process of an integrated lesson in literature and history in high school / Izv. Volgogr. gos. ped. un-ta. - 2007. - No. 5. - 111-114 p.
2. Hovhannisyan L.A., Myslivets S.A. Integration processes in the regional system of secondary vocational education Tavrishesky scientific observer. 2015. No. 1. pp. 53-55.
3. Shogan V.V. Methods of teaching history at school: a new technology of personality-oriented historical education. - Rostov-on-Don: Phoenix, 2007. - 475 p.

4. Yatsenko L. V. The picture of the world as a universal means of regulation /
The scientific picture of the world as a component of the modern worldview. - 2000.
38-64 p. Pedagogy